

Access to a Concentrated Academic Core: Non-Core Intermediaries and Budget-Dependent Disruption in Global Mobility Networks

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Global academic mobility is commonly studied in terms of destinations, prestige hierarchies, or aggregate movement patterns across institutions and countries [5, 6, 7]. However, when inbound mobility is highly concentrated in a very small institutional core, access to that core may depend not only on the destinations themselves but also on the pathways that connect non-core institutions to them. Inspired by recent work on structurally critical intermediaries and flow-based influence in complex networks [3, 4], this extended abstract asks whether a small set of non-core institutions disproportionately mediates access to a concentrated academic core in a global institution-level mobility network.

We construct an institution-level mobility graph from ORCID-derived affiliation transitions [1, 2]. Institutions are linked by observed mobility edges, and the destination core is defined as the minimum set of institutions accounting for 50% of total inbound mobility. We then quantify non-core gatekeeping through shortest-path mediation from non-core institutions to the core, and compare three node-removal strategies: gatekeeping-based targeting, inbound-size-based targeting, and random removal. For each strategy, we measure the remaining fraction of non-core institutions that can still reach at least one core institution.

The results show that the destination side of academic mobility is highly concentrated: only 1.42% of institutions account for 50.0% of inbound mobility. Within the non-core, gatekeeping is itself highly concentrated and only partially overlaps with inbound size. In the removal experiment, gatekeeping-based targeting is the most disruptive strategy under small removal budgets, dominating from 1% to 32% removal, with a brief mid-budget re-entry. By contrast, larger-budget disruption is more strongly driven by high-inflow non-core institutions, while random removal remains consistently less disruptive.

These findings suggest that access to elite academic destinations is pathway-dependent. A small set of non-core institutions acts as structurally important intermediaries under targeted, small-budget disruption, whereas larger-budget vulnerability is more closely tied to institution size. More broadly, the results show that understanding academic mobility requires attention not only to where scholars end up, but also to which non-core institutions mediate access to a concentrated institutional core [3, 4]. This perspective may also help identify vulnerable mobility pathways in research systems, especially where access to elite destinations depends on a small number of intermediary institutions.

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Figure 1: Concentrated academic core and budget-dependent disruption. (A) The destination core is highly concentrated: 1.42% of institutions account for 50.0% of inbound mobility. (B) Difference in remaining non-core reachability between gatekeeping-based and inbound-size-based removal. Negative values indicate stronger disruption by non-core gatekeepers. Gatekeeping dominates at small budgets (1–32%), with a brief mid-budget re-entry; the far-right tail mainly reflects a ratio effect.